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The Impact of Climate Change on Water Stress in a Highly Regulated River: Sensitivity to Changes in Energy Demand, Water Use, and Regulations

Trine Jahr Hegdahl ¹ Kolbjørn Engeland ¹, Shaochun Huang ¹, Emiliano Gelati ², Carl Andreas Veie ¹

¹ Norges Vassdrags- Og Energidirektorat (NVE), Oslo, Norway

² University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

Climate projections for the Drammen River basin indicate a slight increase in annual runoff with an increase during winter and a decrease during summer. These changes in runoff will, in conjunction with changes in energy demand, regulations (licensing) of hydropower reservoirs, domestic, industrial and agricultural water demand, affect energy production and the severity of water stress events.

As part of the HorizonEurope STARS4Water project, the aim of this study is to combine climate projections with different narratives for energy demand, environmental restrictions (regulations) and water demand to identify when it is more likely that critical situations violating regulatory constraints might occur, and if the frequency and severity of such events will change. This information can guide planning and optimization of available water resources.

We first estimate changes in water availability and energy production for CMIP5-RCP4.5 projections using three combinations of GCM and RCMs combined with two different downscaling methods (Climate in Norway 2100 NCCS report no. 1/2017, Hanssen-Bauer et al 2017). The HBV and LISFLOOD hydrologic models are used to calculate changes in runoff for a future period as compared to a reference period.

Subsequently, the simulated runoff is used as input to the One-area Power-market Simulator EOPS (aka VansimTap) to estimate changes in energy production, reservoir water level and environmental flows. In a second step, we investigate how narratives of selected socio-economic developments might affect water stress in the basin. The narratives include changes in energy demand regulations (licensing) and water demand.